

Addition of Aromatic Heterocyclic Amines to Nickel (II) and Cobalt (II) Bis Kozates

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There has been considerable interest¹⁻⁷ in the adduct formation of nickel (II) and cobalt(II) acetylacetonates with co-ordinating solvents. Nothing has appeared so far in the literature concerning the adducts of closely related kozic acid. This communication relates to the adduct formation of nickel (II) and cobalt (II) kozates with aromatic heterocyclic nitrogenous bases like pyridine, β -picoline and γ -picoline.

The adducts of nickel (II) and cobalt(II) kozates were obtained with the above heterocyclic nitrogenous bases by treating an aqueous solution of nickel(II) chloride/cobalt(II) chloride with an aqueous solution containing kozic acid and the donor base and subsequent cooling. α -picoline does not form well defined complexes which may be ascribed to the possible steric hindrance offered by the α -methyl group. Nickel(II) adducts are dirty green and cobalt(II) adducts are brownish yellow in colour. Whereas cobalt(II) complexes slowly lose the heterocyclic base when left in air for some days or on being heated, nickel (II) complexes do not lose the heterocyclic base even on heating at 110°. Nickel(II) systems are more stable than cobalt(II) systems, which observation is in line with the corresponding acetylacetonate complexes^{4,5,8}. Attempts to prepare adducts containing bidentate chelating amines like ortho-phenanthroline and 2-2'-dipyridyl were unsuccessful.

The stereochemistry of nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes as indicated by magnetochemical data is of much current interest. The magnetic moments of tetrahedral nickel(II) complexes and octahedral cobalt (II) complexes are higher than the spin only value due to very large orbital contributions arising out of degenerate ground states. A magnetic moment ranging from 3.5 to 4.2 B.M. is associated with tetrahedral nickel (II) complexes and a moment 4.7 to 5.3 B.M. with high spin octahedral cobalt(II) compounds. On the other hand moments of octahedral nickel(II) complexes run from 2.83 to 3.4 B.M. and of tetrahedral cobalt(II) complexes from 4.1 to 4.7 B.M.⁹⁻¹³ From the observed magnetic moments

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[nickel (II) complexes, $\mu_{\text{eff}}=2.9-3.1$ B.M.]; cobalt (II) complexes $\mu_{\text{eff}}=4.9-5.1$ B.M.], it may be concluded that these adducts are octahedral.

The insolubility of these complexes in water and common organic solvents prevented us to study the conductance and electronic absorption spectra of the complexes in solution. The solid reflectance spectra might have given some light to the structure of these complexes. Unfortunately our laboratory is not equipped to do this.

The formula of the complexes, $[M(\text{amine})_2L_2]$ (where amine=pyridine, β -picoline and γ -picoline and LH = a molecule of koziic acid), their paramagnetism suggest that these compounds have an octahedral arrangement with pyridine (β -picoline or γ -picoline) molecules tentatively on the apical sites of the metal atom.

EXPERIMENTAL

Nickel (II) chloride hexahydrate and cobalt (II) chloride hexahydrate were B.D.H.'s product. Pyridine, β -picoline and γ -picoline were Hopkin & William's (London) product. Koziic acid was B.D.H. L.R. variety and used directly.

General method of synthesis of the adducts. $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.01M) was dissolved in minimum amount of water. Koziic acid (0.01M) was dissolved in the requisite aqueous heterocyclic base (water, 5ml; base, 1 ml). These two solutions were mixed and allowed to stand overnight in a frigidaire. The microcrystals formed were filtered off, washed with ethanol, dried in air for one day and analysed. The complexes are insoluble in water, alcohol, chloroform, ether and benzene.

TABLE I

Analysis and physical properties of nickel (II) and cobalt (II) complexes

Compound	Colour	Analysis		Magnetic moment at 305°K B. M.
		Found %	Reqd. %	
1. $[\text{Ni}(\text{Py})_2(\text{Koz})_2]$	Dirty green	Ni, 11.60 N, 5.82	11.82 5.61	3.10
2. $[\text{Ni}(\beta\text{-Pic})_2(\text{Koz})_2]$	Dirty green	Ni, 11.01 N, 5.55	11.19 5.31	2.92
3. $[\text{Ni}(\gamma\text{-Pic})_2(\text{Koz})_2]$	Dirty green	Ni, 10.92 N, 5.59	11.19 5.31	2.95
4. $[\text{Co}(\text{Py})_2(\text{Koz})_2]$	Brownish yellow	Co, 11.95 N, 5.42	11.82 5.61	5.05
5. $[\text{Co}(\beta\text{-Pic})_2(\text{Koz})_2]$	Brownish yellow	Co, 11.36 N, 5.12	11.19 5.31	5.10
6. $[\text{Co}(\gamma\text{-Pic})_2(\text{Koz})_2]$	Brownish yellow	Co, 10.91 N, 5.00	10.82 5.13	4.95

where Py=pyridine, β -Pic=3-methylpyridine, γ Pic = 4-methylpyridine and Koz=koziic acid

Analysis. Nickel was estimated by decomposing the complex by boiling with conc. HCl for half an hour and finally precipitating nickel with dimethylglyoxime. Cobalt was analysed by decomposing the complex with conc. HNO₃ and conc. HCl and then treating with conc. H₂SO₄ and finally weighing as anhydrous CoSO₄. Nitrogen was estimated by semimicro Duma's combustion technique.

Magnetic Susceptibility Measurements. Magnetic measurements of the complexes at room temperature were made by the Gouy method using recrystallised copper sulphate pentahydrate as the standard and applying a field strength of about 7.8×10^3 gauss.

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